

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ntrakwah****FIRST NAME: Kwadwo****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord version 16.0 on MacBook)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 25–32)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33–39)
3. CMS Crib Sheet (EUCLID 2021, 43–58)
4. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58–64)
5. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6–12)
6. Zotero (EUCLID 2016)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have thoroughly reviewed the ACA-401D course material (EUCLID 2021). It is an easy read and a brilliant introduction to international academic writing. Irrespective of the level of a candidate, the course material helps bring every candidate up to the same level. It covers areas such as essay writing, punctuation, and plagiarism and helps a candidate distinguish between US and UK English.

In this response paper, I discuss critical academic writing concepts such as American and British English, plagiarism, Latin abbreviations and expressions, academic writing software, and others.

2) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The course material highlights that American English is currently dominant in the world English (EUCLID 2021, 25). I found this to be very informative. Coming from a

Commonwealth country, my education has mainly been in British English, so I always thought British English was the dominant influence.

Some of the differences in usage between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) (EUCLID 2021, 26) highlighted by the course material were very instructive. For example, the differences in usage with SBE ‘Large Collective Nouns’ and Differences in usage with SBE ‘Pluralised Adjectives’ were exciting highlights.

Although it may be seen as basic, the discussion on periods, commas, quotations, punctuation with business and social letters, and how they are used in SAE and SBE formats was critical. For example, in letter writing with SBE, there is no period after a title, while SAE has a period after the title (EUCLID 2021, 32). It also highlighted the importance of ensuring that the settings on various devices were set to the appropriate language for the work.

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when ‘the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information’ (EUCLID 2021, 34). An example of plagiarism is ‘Taking someone else’s words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author’ (EUCLID 2021, 34). The definition and examples given are very apt as they highlight in simple terms what plagiarism is.

In particular, the reference to having to give credit after you paraphrase was a great refresher. It is common practice to see people paraphrasing someone’s work and not crediting the author.

The study material used the question-and-answer approach in discussing when to give credit to the author, why to mention the source, and how to cite, among others. This was very good. It made the text very engaging and easy for me to follow.

The course material has improved my understanding of in-text citations and the format to follow when citing books or online works.

4) CMS CRIB SHEET

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) ‘Chicago Style’ is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003 and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press). While sometimes reference is made to ‘Turabian style’, this is simply the Chicago style applied to the research papers (EUCLID 2021, 44).

This was the most illuminating area for me in the study material. Before reviewing the material, I knew little about the CMS or style guides. The material has improved my understanding of CMS considerably. I strongly recommend the study material to anybody looking for a PhD.

In particular, the study material has highlighted for me the need to be consistent in the usage of internet terminology and the use of a dictionary as the best guide when it comes to the spelling and usage of compound words.

I also have ambitions of writing a book. The study material has highlighted that a style guide is essential in academic writing. As a result, I will have to adopt an internationally recognised style guide such as the CMS when I am writing my book.

5) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

My training as a lawyer involved the use of a lot of Latin terms. However, the terrain has changed recently, and we have been encouraged to use simple English. It is refreshing to see that in academic writing, it is also best to use ‘the plain language principles (EUCLID 2021, 59).

Plain language ‘is a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing. When writing in plain language, use short sentences with simple words. Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 59). The use of simple words in communication cannot be emphasized enough. From my experience, many people believe that good writing must involve complex and convoluted sentences with big words when that is not true.

I always use the example of a brilliant young lawyer at my office who is great at the law but has a big challenge communicating with clients. He uses complex and technical courtroom language even when communicating with clients. As a result, some clients have even had the course to complain. I will urge him to look for a similar standard abbreviations table to that in the course material (EUCLID 2021, 59–64) and apply it in his communication with clients.

6) ESSAY WRITING

It was exciting and refreshing to see essay writing as part of the course material. As a student, I have been writing essays for a long time. However, essay writing has never been taught so extensively in all my years of academic study.

The tips on starting the essay, researching the topic organising your ideas, and writing the essay itself were a welcome refresher course for me. Regarding writing a paper, the various rules of thumb discussed were also very relevant.

I was particularly excited by the rule of thumb: ‘Do not make writing boring and clumsy’ (EUCLID 2021, 13). I find that to be a key component in any writing. In practice, people tend to shy away from boring and clumsy material. Throughout the course, I hope to master the art of making my writing enjoyable.

7) ZOTERO

Zotero is a brilliant tool, and I am incredibly grateful to the faculty for introducing this to the course. I still need to perfect my use of it, but I am sure that with more practice, I will improve at using Zotero.

I recall years ago when I was doing my master’s. Whenever I was researching, I would copy and paste various articles in full in Word so that I could later refer to these articles. It was such a tedious process.

With the assistance of Zotero and its library and citation function, research has become much easier and more efficient. At the click of a button, research material is easily stored in your Zotero library and then quickly added to the Word document for references, among others.

8) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I found the study material extremely useful and recommend it highly to anyone looking to do a Ph.D. Before deciding to embark on the Ph.D. journey, I got the sense that you had just dropped into an ocean and asked to do research without any assistance. This material has been very encouraging as you get the sense that by reading it and mastering it, your hands are being held, and you are being guided step by step in academic writing.

Introducing technology such as Zotero to the process has become a welcome addition to my writing arsenal.

Irrespective of how many documents you may have written, academic writing is unique, so candidates must master this document and apply it accordingly.

The Grammarly settings have been customised for candidates, which is good. However, the ‘Dialect’ is locked in for American English. Therefore, although we can write in American or British English, the Grammarly settings slightly restrict this. Consequently, I recommend that candidates be allowed to edit the ‘Dialect’ section of Grammarly.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Turabian, Kate L. 2013. "A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations." Eighth Edition. Accessed 10 January 2024. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/turabian.html>.

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